

Effect of Short-term Treated Wastewater Application on Physiological Traits and Stress-related Genes (*CaCAT2*, *CaDREB32*, *CaLOX1*) in Pepper

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Abstract

This study investigated the effects of treated wastewater irrigation on physiological traits and gene expression in pepper (*Capsicum annuum*) plants during early development. Control (tap water) and treated wastewater treatments were compared, and physiological parameters, including SPAD values and leaf color measurements, were assessed. In addition, the expression levels of stress-related genes *CaCAT2*, *CaDREB32*, and *CaLOX1* were analyzed using RT-qPCR. The results showed that treated wastewater irrigation significantly enhanced leaf chlorophyll content and caused a shift in leaf coloration toward darker, greenish tones. At the molecular level, a moderate upregulation of *CaCAT2* was detected, whereas *CaDREB32* exhibited only a slight and statistically insignificant change. The most pronounced response was observed for *CaLOX1*, which showed an approximately 50% increase in expression under treated wastewater treatment compared with the control. These findings suggest that treated wastewater irrigation can temporarily enhance photosynthetic capacity in pepper plants, while concurrently activating stress-related signaling pathways. This dual effect highlights that the agricultural use of treated wastewater entails potential benefits but also carries long-term risks that must be carefully considered.

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1. Introduction

Water scarcity has emerged as one of the most critical challenges to sustainable agriculture, particularly in semiarid and arid regions. The depletion of freshwater resources, driven by climate change and population growth, has rendered the use of alternative irrigation sources in agriculture unavoidable (Qadir et al., 2010). Within this context, treated wastewater reuse is increasingly recognized as a key component of sustainable water management, as it not only alleviates pressure on freshwater supplies but also supports nutrient recycling (Pedrero et al., 2010). Pepper (*Capsicum annuum* L.) is a widely cultivated vegetable of considerable economic importance worldwide. However, pepper plants are highly sensitive to water quality and environmental stresses, which can adversely affect their growth, yield, and physiological performance (Aktas et al., 2006). Previous research has demonstrated that treated wastewater irrigation can induce both physiological and morphological alterations in plants. Nonetheless, the majority of these studies have concentrated on cereals or industrial crops, while comparatively fewer investigations have addressed its effects on vegetable species (Chen et al., 2013; Gatta et al., 2015). The combined evaluation of molecular and physiological indicators is crucial for elucidating plant responses to environmental stresses. In this study, three stress-responsive genes were selected to complement the physiological assessments. *CaDREB32* functions as a transcription factor that enhances tolerance to abiotic stresses, with its expression strongly induced under drought and osmotic stress conditions (Sun et al., 2025). *CaLOX1*, a 9-lipoxygenase in pepper, is particularly activated under pathogen infection and osmotic stress and contributes to defense regulation through its role in reactive oxygen species (ROS)-mediated signaling pathways (Hwang et al., 2010; Lim et al., 2015). Furthermore, the *CaCAT* gene family plays a pivotal role in alleviating oxidative damage by detoxifying ROS such as hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), thereby maintaining cellular homeostasis under stress conditions

(Rodríguez-Ruiz et al., 2019). Together, the analysis of these molecular markers alongside physiological traits offers a more comprehensive understanding of the mechanisms underlying plant adaptation to treated wastewater irrigation. Additionally, SPAD values, which reflect leaf chlorophyll content, and color parameters (L*, a*, b*, chroma, and hue) are widely recognized as reliable indicators for evaluating plant physiological responses to stress (Percival et al., 2008). Integrating these physiological traits with molecular markers provides a more comprehensive framework for understanding the stress-related effects of treated wastewater irrigation on pepper plants. This study aimed to investigate the effects of treated wastewater irrigation on the expression levels of *CaDREB32*, *CaCAT2*, and *CaLOX1* genes, together with leaf chlorophyll content (SPAD) and color parameters in pepper plants. Such an approach enables a more holistic assessment of the molecular and physiological responses of pepper to treated wastewater irrigation, thereby providing deeper insights into its stress physiology.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Plant material and experiment design

The experiment was conducted in controlled climate chambers at the Faculty of Agriculture, Van Yüzüncü Yıl University. During the trial, environmental conditions were maintained at an average daytime temperature of 25 ± 2 °C and a nighttime temperature of 18 ± 2 °C, with relative humidity held between 60–70% and a 16-hour light/8-hour dark photoperiod. The plant material used was the pepper (*Capsicum annuum*) cultivar BT İnce Sivri Kıl Acı 016. Seedlings at the 3–4-leaf stage and of uniform developmental status were transplanted into pots. The experiment was arranged according to a completely randomized factorial design with five replications, using a total of 10 pots. Pots were filled with sieved and air-dried soil before transplanting the seedlings. Irrigation was applied regularly, with equal volumes supplied to each pot to reach pot capacity.

Treated wastewater was obtained from the advanced biological treatment plant in the İskele district of Van province. The effluent, originating from a treatment facility located approximately 5 km from the university, was transported weekly to the experimental site in plastic canisters. Leaf samples for gene expression analysis were collected on day 20 of the experiment, and differences in expression levels were subsequently determined. The 20-day experimental period was designed to capture the physiological and molecular responses occurring during the early developmental stage of pepper seedlings. This short-term exposure covered the critical window in which stress perception and the activation of initial defense mechanisms take place, enabling the evaluation of early responses before long-term acclimation or cumulative effects emerge.

2.2. Chlorophyll and color analysis

For chlorophyll determination, ten measurements were taken from the leaves of plants in each pot using a SPAD-502 chlorophyll meter. The mean of these values, automatically calculated by the device, was recorded as the SPAD value for each pot (Tüfenkci and Yerli, 2023). Leaf color was assessed based on the color space parameters L^* , a^* , C° , and h° , using a chromameter (Minolta CR-400; Osaka, Japan). For each

replicate, ten leaves were randomly selected, and color measurements were performed on these samples.

2.3. Gene expression analysis

For gene expression analyses, leaf samples from each treatment were collected in three biological replicates on day 20 of the experiment and stored at -80°C until RNA isolation. Prior to isolation, frozen leaf tissues were ground into a fine powder using liquid nitrogen. RNA was extracted with TRIzol reagent (Nucleogene), and RNA purity and concentration were assessed using a NanoDrop spectrophotometer (Thermo Scientific). Complementary DNA (cDNA) synthesis was carried out with the Solver cDNA Synthesis Kit (SLV-M-2021-007) after diluting RNA samples to a final concentration of $10\text{ ng}/\mu\text{L}$. Quantitative real-time PCR (RT-qPCR) was then performed using Solver qPCR Master Mix (SLV-M-2021-002) on a Rotor-Gene Q9000 system (Qiagen). To minimize experimental error, all PCR reactions were conducted in duplicate. A total of four genes were analyzed: three target genes (*CaLOX1*, *CaDREB32*, *CaCAT2*) and *CaUBQ3*, which served as the reference gene. Gene-specific primer sequences, annealing temperatures, and accession numbers are listed in Table 1. *CaUBQ3* was used as the internal control for normalization of Ct values in RT-qPCR.

Table 1. Primer name, nucleotide sequences and annealing temperatures

Gene Name	Forward Sequence	Reverse Sequence	Annealing Temperature
<i>CaCAT2</i>	GAAGCCAAATCCTAAGTCCC	CCAACTCGGATTGCCTCTT	57 °C
<i>CaLOX1</i>	TGCAGGTTACCTCCAAATCGCCCA	CTATATCGACACACTGTTGGGTATTCCCTT	57 °C
<i>CaDREB32</i>	CTTTATCATCGTTGGTATCCGC	TAACCAGCCTGTTTCCATAGTT	58 °C
<i>CaUBQ3</i>	TGTCCATCTGCTCTCTGTG	CACCCCAAGCACAAATAAGAC	57 °C

2.4. Statistical analysis

Data obtained from the study were statistically analyzed using the SPSS software package. Differences between the control and treated wastewater groups were assessed with an independent samples t-test, and homogeneity of variances was verified using Levene's test. In all analyses, a significance level of $p < 0.05$ was applied. Gene expression levels were calculated using the relative quantification

method described by Livak and Schmittgen (2001).

3. Results

3.1. Chlorophyll and color analysis

Analysis of leaf color parameters revealed that L^* , a^* , and b^* values were significantly higher in the control group than in the treated wastewater group ($p < 0.05$) (Table 2). In wastewater-treated plants, a decrease in L^* and

an increase (less negative) in a^* values were recorded. Moreover, the marked reduction in b^* values indicated a significant decline in yellow tones in the leaves. The Chroma (Ch)

value was also lower in the treated wastewater group, while $H^{\circ}ab$ values were higher, reflecting a shift in leaf color toward greener hues.

Table 2. Effect of wastewater on color parameters of pepper leaves

	Control	Treated-wastewater	p-value
L	48.73±1.68	39.45±1.18	0.00
a	-17.36±0.51	-13.50±0.41	0.00
b	34.78±1.57	20.44±1.16	0.00
Ch	33.66±2.04	31.45±0.52	0.00
H[°]ab	117.49±0.84	123.24±0.77	0.00

Data were shown as means ± SE. Differences between groups were analyzed by independent samples t-test. ($p < 0.05$). L*, (+) brightness, (-) darkness; a^* , (+) redness, (-) greenness; b^* , (+) yellowness, (-) blueness; Ch, Chroma; $H^{\circ}ab$, Hue.

SPAD analysis showed that chlorophyll content in pepper leaves was significantly higher in the wastewater treatment group compared with the control. The mean SPAD

value was 26.29 in the control group and 34.74 in the wastewater group, with the difference found to be highly significant ($p < 0.05$) (Table 3).

Table 3. SPAD values in pepper plants

	SPAD	p-value
Control	26.29±0.54	0.00
Treated Wastewater	34.74±0.62	0.00

Data were shown as means ± SE (n=10). Differences between groups were analyzed by independent samples t-test ($p < 0.05$).

3.2. Gene expression analysis

On day 20 of the experiment, the expression levels of *CaCAT2*, *CaDREB32*, and *CaLOXI* were examined in pepper leaves under treated wastewater and tap water treatments. Distinct expression patterns were observed between the control and treated wastewater groups. In the case of *CaCAT2*, expression was at basal levels

in the control group irrigated with tap water, whereas it increased by approximately 40% in the treated wastewater group. While expression increased about one-fold in the control group, it rose to approximately 1.4-fold in pepper leaves irrigated with treated wastewater compared with the control (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Relative gene expression rate of *CaCAT2*, *CaDREB32* and *CaLOXI* genes in *Capsicum annuum* leaves at day 20 under tap water (control) and treated wastewater treatments (n=3).

For the *CaDREB32* gene, no significant difference was detected between the control and treated wastewater treatments. Expression levels were approximately the same in both groups, with only a slight, non-significant increase observed under treated wastewater irrigation. A significant increase in *CaLOXI*

gene expression was observed. While expression remained at baseline levels in the control group, it rose by approximately 50% under treated wastewater treatment.

4. Discussion

This study examined the effects of treated wastewater irrigation on the physiological characteristics and gene expression of pepper plants during the early growth stage. The results demonstrated that short-term treated wastewater application significantly increased chlorophyll content and caused noticeable alterations in leaf coloration. SPAD analysis revealed an approximately 30% increase in chlorophyll content in the wastewater-treated plants compared with the control group. Color parameter measurements indicated that the leaves of wastewater-treated plants were darker and exhibited greener hues than those of the control group. These findings suggest that treated wastewater may stimulate chlorophyll biosynthesis in pepper plants during early development and influence leaf pigmentation. Similar results have been reported in other crops; for instance, Gassama et al. (2015) observed changes in chlorophyll pigment content in rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) following municipal wastewater irrigation, while Al-Jaloud et al. (1995) found that wastewater application significantly altered pigment composition and mineral content in corn and sorghum. Likewise, Ofori et al. (2024) reported enhanced chlorophyll pigment accumulation in tomato and cabbage irrigated with wastewater. The increase in chlorophyll observed in this study may be attributed to the duration of wastewater exposure, as chlorophyll content and SPAD values are known to vary depending on plant developmental stage, wastewater composition, and treatment period. In addition to these changes in physiological parameters, treated wastewater irrigation also produced differential effects on the expression of the *CaCAT2*, *CaLOX1*, and *CaDREB32* genes during the early growth stage. Catalase (CAT) enzymes constitute one of the key antioxidant defense mechanisms in plants, responsible for the detoxification of reactive oxygen species (ROS) such as hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2). Under environmental stress, excessive ROS production can disrupt membrane integrity and damage proteins and nucleic acids; therefore, catalase activity plays a crucial role in

maintaining cellular redox homeostasis and overall metabolic balance (Apel and Hirt, 2004; Miller et al., 2010). Catalase genes are known to be highly active during the early stages of both biotic and abiotic stress conditions (Mittler et al., 2004). Anderson (2002) examined the relationship between catalase activity, H_2O_2 degradation, and thermotolerance in pepper and reported a decline in catalase activity in older leaves, which was later restored following heat acclimation. The study further demonstrated that pepper possesses catalase isoforms capable of detoxifying exogenous H_2O_2 . These findings indicate that catalase genes in pepper function as a central component of oxidative stress management, responding not only to temperature stress but also to various environmental oxidative challenges. In the present study, treated wastewater treatment increased *CaCAT2* gene expression by approximately 40% compared with the control group. This upregulation may reflect the plant's perception of ionic and organic compounds in the wastewater as mild stressors, triggering antioxidant defense activation to maintain oxidative equilibrium. Short-term wastewater exposure also induced changes at both the physiological and molecular levels. SPAD analysis showed a significant increase in chlorophyll content, while leaf color shifted toward darker green hues, likely due to nutrient-mediated stimulation of chlorophyll biosynthesis. Despite these short-term physiological improvements, gene expression data suggest that the plants simultaneously recognized treated wastewater as a potential stress factor. The pronounced upregulation of the *CaCAT2* gene in plants irrigated with treated wastewater is accompanied by increased SPAD values. This finding suggests that the catalase enzyme mitigates chlorophyll degradation by detoxifying reactive oxygen species (ROS), thereby contributing to the darker green appearance of the leaves. Hence, the elevated *CaCAT2* expression can be interpreted as a defense mechanism that protects chlorophyll under mild oxidative stress induced by treated was. Dehydration-responsive element-binding proteins (DREBs)

are a family of transcription factors that regulate the expression of multiple genes associated with abiotic stress tolerance in plants (Agarwal et al., 2006). DREB transcription factors act as early regulators in plant responses to environmental stresses such as drought, salinity, and heat (Shinozaki and Yamaguchi-Shinozaki, 2007). Sakuma et al. (2002) demonstrated that the *DREB1* and *DREB2* genes in *Arabidopsis* bind to the same DRE/CRT motif but are differentially activated under distinct environmental stress conditions. Similarly, DREB1/CBF transcription factors in rice were shown to regulate cold-responsive genes and enhance cold tolerance in plants (Ito et al., 2006). In the present study, *CaDREB32* expression exhibited only a slight, non-significant increase under short-term treated wastewater treatment compared with the control group. When compared with previous findings (Sakuma et al., 2002; Ito et al., 2006), this limited response may indicate that wastewater exposure induced only mild stress or that members of the *DREB* gene family elicit stress-specific regulatory responses. The observed increase in chlorophyll content and the shift in leaf color toward greenish hues suggest that treated wastewater may have short-term physiological benefits; however, the weak activation of *CaDREB32* indicates that a full molecular stress response was not triggered in pepper plants under these experimental conditions. The limited increase in *CaDREB32* expression is likely attributable to the short treatment duration (20 days) or the relatively mild stress intensity. Previous studies have shown that DREB-type transcription factors are typically activated under prolonged or high-intensity stress conditions (Lata and Prasad, 2011). The most pronounced change observed in this study was in the *CaLOXI* gene, whose expression increased by approximately 50% in the wastewater-treated group compared with the control. The lipoxygenase (*LOX*) gene family encodes enzymes that catalyze the oxidation of polyunsaturated fatty acids, leading to the biosynthesis of bioactive compounds such as oxylipins and jasmonates (JA). *LOX* genes

play essential roles in plant defense responses against insect herbivory and pathogen attack, in adaptation to abiotic stresses such as drought and salinity, and in developmental processes including leaf senescence and fruit ripening (Wasternack and Hause, 2013). Lim et al. (2015) reported that *CaLOXI* expression in *Capsicum annuum* was strongly induced under drought and high-salinity conditions, functioning as part of the osmotic stress response. In the model plant *Arabidopsis*, *LOX* genes have been shown to regulate JA biosynthesis and mediate defense signaling under various environmental stresses. For example, Bell et al. (1995) demonstrated that chloroplast *LOX* is essential for wound-induced JA accumulation, Chauvin et al. (2013) identified four distinct *13-LOX* genes responsible for rapid JA production, and Velloso et al. (2007) reported that the 9-*LOX* pathway contributes to defense responses and root development. Taken together with these findings, the increased expression of *CaLOXI* following treated wastewater irrigation in our study suggests that pepper plants perceive wastewater exposure as an environmental stress cue, leading to the early activation of the *LOX*-mediated oxylipin/JA signaling pathway. Thus, the observed increase in *CaLOXI* expression implies that treated wastewater not only enhances photosynthetic pigment accumulation but also induces oxidative stress signaling. Overall, treated wastewater application appears to exert a dual effect in pepper plants supporting photosynthetic capacity in the short term while simultaneously triggering defense-related pathways and early stress responses. Although this study focused on a short-term (20-day) treatment, the findings particularly the increase in SPAD values, darkening of leaf color, and the upregulation of *CaCAT2*, *CaDREB32*, and *CaLOXI* genes indicate that early defense and antioxidant responses were activated in pepper plants exposed to treated wastewater. These early physiological and molecular responses can be interpreted as part of the plant's short-term acclimation process to treated wastewater conditions. In the long term, however, these responses may stabilize or shift to a different

profile depending on factors such as ion accumulation, nutrient balance, and changes in soil properties. Therefore, conducting long-term studies would provide clearer insights into the transition between short- and long-term responses.

5. Conclusion

This study investigated the effects of treated wastewater irrigation on early-stage physiological traits and gene expression in pepper (*Capsicum annuum*). Wastewater application increased leaf chlorophyll content and caused a shift in leaf color toward darker green tones, indicating a short-term enhancement of photosynthetic capacity. At the molecular level, a moderate increase in *CaCAT2* expression suggested the activation of antioxidant defense mechanisms, whereas *CaDREB32* exhibited only a limited and non-significant change, implying a weak early stress perception. The most pronounced response was observed in *CaLOX1*, which showed an approximately 50% increase in expression, indicating the early activation of oxylipin/jasmonate (JA)-mediated stress signaling. Overall, these findings demonstrate that treated wastewater exerts a dual effect on pepper plants during early development enhancing photosynthetic performance while concurrently activating stress-related pathways. While treated wastewater reuse may offer agronomic advantages, it also presents potential long-term physiological and molecular risks. Therefore, further research involving different plant species, treatment durations, and treated wastewater compositions is essential to evaluate the sustainability and safety of wastewater use in agricultural irrigation. Moreover, sustainable management strategies and regular monitoring of soil and crop quality are required to minimize potential long-term environmental impacts of wastewater reuse.

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